

SCALING-UP LIGNOCELLULOSIC BUTANOL PRODUCTION (BUTANEXT)

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ABSTRACT: The ButaNexT project aims to demonstrate the techno-economic feasibility of the conversion of two sustainable lignocellulosic feedstocks (wheat straw and miscanthus) available at EU level, into biobutanol through the integration of different technology developments. The project has ended recently and the main achievements of the consortium have been the following: (1) design, construction and operation of a micronizing pilot prototype for controlled biomass particle size production up to 0.5 mm with a more reduced energy consumption and able to be scalable to industrial size; (2) development of a flexible and easy to adapt two-step fractionation process based on the combination of the micronizing prototype with a continuous thermochemical pretreatment; (3) development of tailored enzyme cocktails (MetZyme® SUNO™) that address harsh process-specific conditions and facilitate improved hydrolysis of pretreated biomass to monosaccharides; (4) development of a Clostridial strain able to ferment cellulosic sugars effectively (target butanol yield > 0.25 g/g pure sugar) and having 20% higher butanol tolerance than baseline strain; (5) development of a patent-pending “In situ product recovery process” based on improved pervaporation fluxes obtained during fermentation that allows continuous operation; (6) validation of the technical performance of the individual stages cited above in a pilot facility using wheat straw as feedstock from handling to product recovery in a 100 L bioreactor; (7) testing of properties and performance of butanol as a blend component in both diesel and gasoline fuels and (8) calculation of GHG emissions of biobutanol in a number of different scenarios based on the use of wheat straw and miscanthus as feedstocks and for the provision of heat, electricity and waste water treatment.

Keywords: liquid biofuel, fermentation, wheat straw, pilot plant, sustainability

1 INTRODUCTION

The EU transport sector is still highly dependent on fossil energy carriers and is responsible for nearly a quarter of EU's greenhouse gas emissions [1]. Across all transport modes, the major energy consumer is road transport which represents 81.7%, followed by air (13.9%), rail (2%) and water (1.6%) [2].

The 2030 Climate and Energy package [3] calls for significant measures for decarbonizing transport, EU targets of 20% GHG reduction in transports in 2030 relative to the emissions 2008 and 60% reduction in 2050, relative to the emissions from transport in 1990.

On November 2016 the European Commission issued the Winter Package [4] which included a comprehensive revision of the Renewable Energy Directive, COM (2016) 767 final, (RED II). The Renewable and Advanced biofuels industry is the only player in the EU that can ensure the deployment of sustainable fuels for decarbonising the transport sector, especially heavy road and air transport. For this reason new and more sustainable drop-in biofuel alternatives are being pursued with the aim of overcoming the current challenges and limitations exhibited by bioethanol and biodiesel through R&D projects as Next Generation Butanol (ButaNexT).

The ButaNexT project aims to develop a highly efficient production process for the conversion of sustainable lignocellulosic feedstocks) into biobutanol

through the integration of different technology developments.

Butanol is a four carbon alcohol that can be used as a transport fuel. It has traditionally been produced by ABE (1) fermentation (the anaerobic conversion of carbohydrates by strains of Clostridium into acetone, butanol and ethanol). However, there are some important techno-economic issues with ABE fermentation: costs, the relatively low-yield and sluggish fermentations, and some problems caused by end product inhibition and phage infections, made ABE butanol uncompetitive on a commercial scale with butanol produced synthetically from oil and almost all ABE production ceased as the petrochemical industry evolved.

Nevertheless, there is now increasing interest in use of biobutanol as a transport fuel due to the following benefits [5]:

- Higher energy content—Biobutanol's energy content is relatively high among gasoline alternatives.
- Lower Reid vapor pressure—when compared with ethanol, biobutanol has a lower vapor pressure, which means lower volatility and evaporative emissions.
- Increased energy security—Biobutanol can be produced domestically from a variety of feedstocks, while creating jobs.
- Fewer emissions—Carbon dioxide captured by

growing feedstocks reduces overall greenhouse gas emissions by balancing carbon dioxide released from burning biobutanol

Existing biobutanol production is largely from sugars, whereas this project targets lignocellulosic feedstocks including wheat straw and miscanthus.

The following article will show the final results from the project regarding the scale-up of ButaNexT process.

2 BUTANEXT OVERVIEW

The ABE fermentation process has been improved significantly since it was patented by Weizman in 1915 [6]. However, using it to convert lignocellulosic feedstocks remains technical challenging. In order to overcome this, the ButaNexT project started in May 2015 with the aim to develop, optimise and integrate several novel and advanced technologies for the production of sustainable, more efficient and versatile biobutanol from lignocellulosic feedstocks and wastes. This was expected to be achieved by addressing the following technical, economic and environmental challenges:

- Efficient Conversion of Lignocellulosic Feedstocks into Fermentable Sugars through physical and thermochemical pretreatment and enzymatic hydrolysis.
- High Productivity Fermentation for Biobutanol with “in-situ” product recovery.
- Process Integration and Scale-up.
- Techno/Economic Feasibility of Advanced Biofuels Production.
- Blending and Performance.
- Environmental and Social Benefits Assessment of Advanced Biofuels Production.

In April 2018, the ButaNexT project has reached the end of its life, and very significant results have been achieved during these 36 months as described in former proceedings from the 24EUBCE [7] and 25EUBCE [8].

3 SUSTAINABLE FEEDSTOCKS ASSESSMENT

A feedstock assessment has been carried out by E4tech taking into account the availability across Europe of four types of feedstock that can be potentially used for ButaNexT process: wheat straw, miscanthus, the organic fraction of municipal solid waste and woody residues.

The assessment found that even when existing uses of straw are taken into account, and the requirement to leave some on the fields, a significant straw resource of 58.4Mt is available across all EU member states (enough for roughly 158 commercial-scale biobutanol plants). However this is widely distributed across many countries, and competition for straw as an energy feedstock may intensify in the future. The availability of Miscanthus grown on unused or underutilised land was also assessed, as this avoids the risk of indirect land use change (ILUC) which can occur if Miscanthus is grown on existing cropland. Based on the total availability of this type of land within the EU, roughly 20.3Mt/year Miscanthus could be grown (enough to support 45 commercial scale biobutanol plants). However as this land is likely to be highly distributed, the actual potential may be far lower. The resource potential of municipal solid waste and

woody residues was also assessed, although these are currently lower priority feedstocks for the consortium.

4 BIOMASS FRACTIONATION

Initially the feedstocks used for the development of the process were miscanthus, wheat straw and the organic fraction of municipal solid waste. However, the last one was rejected during the first months of the project due to its low sugar content that cannot make the conversion process economically viable.

The following subsections show the process stages involved in the fractionation of the biomass for the solubilisation of the monomeric sugars (glucose, xylose, etc.) available.

4.1. Flexible two-stage pretreatment process

Técnicas Reunidas together with CENER have developed a two-step pre-treatment process which is able to convert different lignocellulosic biomass providing higher yields in sugar release during enzymatic hydrolysis.

It is composed of a new milling prototype (designed and constructed by Técnicas Reunidas) which significantly reduces the biomass particle size (up to less than a 0.5 millimetres). This allows for milder conditions in the subsequent thermochemical stage and an improved conversion rate during the later enzymatic hydrolysis.

With this new equipment is expected that both capital and operating costs can be reduced. In fact, the milling prototype reduces the energy consumption up to 25% compared to the conventional technologies studied.

Figure 1: Pre-treatment micronizing unit (Source: TR/CENER)

With the aim of increasing saccharification yields out of the feedstocks, after micronization the material was subjected to a thermochemical pretreatment in a continuous horizontal reactor unit owned by CENER, providing afterwards a material more prone to enzymatic hydrolysis. Several optimization assays have been carried out in order to increase sugar yield in close cooperation with MetGen’s enzymatic solutions.

4.2 Tailor made enzyme cocktails

Within ButaNexT project, MetGen’s activities towards the development of drop-in enzymatic solutions for the efficient saccharification of selected pretreated feedstocks - wheat straw and miscanthus have resulted in

a selection of tailored MetZyme® SUNO™ enzyme solutions that can be produced in industrial scale and applied to pilot-scale assays in ButaNexT for the production of biobutanol.

During the development process, MetGen considered the following main specification targets: 1) improved sugar yields through biomass specificity, 2) upscalability of enzymatic solutions through addressing the complexity of formulations and 3) reduced production cost through a careful choice of formulation components.

As a result of extensive development work, MetGen was able to improve the hydrolysis efficiency of its initial offering significantly. The developed enzyme cocktails for specific feedstocks were identified and increased total sugar yield from 70% to 90% compared to the baseline ones, in half of the hydrolysis time. On top of the technical performance, other aspects were also considered during the development work, including upscalability and production cost. These considerations enabled finding of more economical feasible alternatives with similar technical performance.

MetGen has been able to supply pilot-scale quantities of improved enzymatic solutions to the ButaNex consortium, demonstrating MetGen's capability to produce and supply MetZyme® SUNO™ solutions in required quantities and in a timely manner. This has been possible due to utilization of MetGen's technology platform ENZINE® which allows fast, flexible and adaptable development of tailor-made enzyme solutions from lab-scale to industrial scale for biorefinery applications.

Within ButaNexT project, MetGen has designed and developed tailor-made enzyme solutions for lignocellulosic feedstocks. This has been done after an extensive screening of different enzyme combinations and formulations. The new enzymatic cocktails for specific feedstocks were identified and increased total sugar yield from 70% to 90% compared to the baseline ones, in half of the hydrolysis time. Enzyme production has been scale-up to pilot scale (400 liters) at MetGen's facilities.

5 HIGH-PRODUCTIVITY FERMENTATION PROCESS

5.1. Development of a Clostridial strain able to ferment cellulosic sugar effectively

Green Biologics (GBL) used experimental evolution techniques to generate strains with improved tolerance to butanol and inhibitory compounds typically found in lignocellulosic hydrolysates. The strains developed demonstrated sustained higher sugar uptake rates in the presence of 20% higher maximum butanol titre than the control strain and fermentation tests using wheat straw and miscanthus feedstocks also showed that the inhibitor tolerant strains exceeded the target solvent productivities by 21% and 75% respectively. The strains developed by GBL have performed well in continuous fermentation systems with in situ product recovery (ISPR) developed by VITO and successfully scaled up to 100 L by CENER.

5.2. Development of a patent-pending "In situ product recovery process"

Butanol productivities can be even further increased when the inhibitory solvents are removed from the fermentation broth while being produced. VITO has

extensive experience in the development of a hybrid fermentation concept which consists of coupling membrane technology (organophilic pervaporation) to the fermentor to achieve "in situ" product recovery (ISPR).

This configuration not only alleviates product inhibition on microorganisms but also leads to partial product purification and enrichment, thus improving water balances and reducing energy consumption in further downstream processing.

In ButaNexT, VITO has evaluated and optimised this ISPR concept with the newly developed strains from GBL. The main objective is to maximise butanol productivity from the selected biomass feedstocks. After an intensive work it was found that continuous operation during fermentation performed better than (fed)-batch conditions in terms of labour intensity, water consumption, solvent enrichment and volumetric productivity. This innovative approach, that also involves the use of high performance alternative membranes, was patented.

6 PROCESS INTEGRATION AND UPSCALING

One of the specific objectives of the project is the validation of the technical performance of the whole ButaNexT process (from feedstock handling to product separation) in a centralised pilot facility. This facility is located at CENER's Biorefinery and Bioenergy Centre (BIO2C) in Aoiz (Spain).

6.1. Pilot plant definition

Initially the pilot plant lay out definition of was done taking into account ButaNexT process sequence and the size of the different equipment involved. However, since the operation was not going to be carried out in continuous mode for the whole configuration, it was agreed that those stages operating in batch mode could be separated from the rest.

The following table shows the different process stages, the equipment used and the operation mode:

Process stage	Equipment used (owner)	Transferred equipment	Operation mode
Chopping	Chopper (CENER)	NO	BATCH
Micronising	Micronising prototype (Técnicas Reunidas)	YES	BATCH
Thermochemical pretreatment	Thermochemical pretreatment reactor (CENER)	NO	BATCH
Enzymatic hydrolysis	Enzymatic hydrolysis reactor (CENER)	NO	BATCH
Filtration of hydrolysate	Filter press (CENER, hired)	Hired	BATCH
Fermentation	100 litre fermentor (CENER.)	NO	CONTINUOUS
Pervaporation	Pervaporation unit (VITO)	YES	CONTINUOUS

Table 1: Process stages and equipment used for the pilot plant configuration

Once the transferred and hired equipment were placed and commissioned, the next step was the start of operation taking into account the other equipment available in CENER.

6.2. Feedstock selection

The initial step was the selection of the feedstock for carrying out the assays at the pilot plant. The process was based on the results obtained in the optimisation of the individual stages developed in WP2 and WP3 (processability and conversion rate) and other aspects studied in WP6 (sustainability and costs). The following table shows a scheme of the qualitative comparison carried out:

	Partner	Wheat Straw	Miscanthus
1) Mechanical pretreatment	TR	● ●	● ●
2) Thermochemical pretreatment	CENER	● ●	● ●
3) Enzymatic hydrolysis and filtration	METGEN/ CENER	● ●	● ●
4) Fermentation	GBL/VITO	●	● ●
5) Sustainability issues (feedstock)	E4tech	●	●
6) Other (price, etc.)	ALL	●	●

● Good ● Medium ● Bad

Table 2: Feedstock selection summary

6.3. Pilot plant operation

During the initial process stages (from mechanical pretreatment to enzymatic hydrolysis), the operation was carried out in batches. The following table shows the total amount of material produced during each stage of the process:

Process stage	Material	Amount	Properties
Micronisation	Micronised wheat straw	961 kg	Particle size 0.5 mm
Thermochemical pretreatment	Pretreated wheat straw (slurry)	519 kg	Moisture 65%
Enzymatic hydrolysis + filtration	Wheat straw hydrolysate	520 kg	Sugar concentration 110 g/l

Table 3: Material produced at CENER's Biorefinery and Bioenergy Centre (BIO2C).

A technician from TR visited CENER to carry out the micronisation of the wheat straw to be used for the assays (Figure 1). The following stage was the preparation of the sugar-rich hydrolysate. CENER technicians carried out the thermochemical pretreatment and produced 519 kg of slurry for the assays (Figure 2). After pretreatment this pretreated material was sequentially subjected to enzymatic hydrolysis using enzymes supplied by MetGen (Figure 3) at high total solids content (20-25%). The hydrolysate produced was filtered using a filter press to avoid the presence of particles that could alter the operation of the pervaporation unit (Figure 4). The amount of filtered hydrolysate obtained was 520 kg with an average sugar concentration of 110 g/l.

Figure 2: Thermochemical pretreatment equipment. (Source: CENER)

Figure 3: Enzymatic hydrolysis reactor. (Source: CENER)

Figure 4: Filtration of the hydrolysate obtained after enzymatic hydrolysis stage (Source: CENER)

Technicians from GBL and VITO visited CENER's premises for training and commissioning of the fermentation and pervaporation processes.

In the case of the fermentation, the upscaling process has been more complex due to the integration of many

factors: microorganisms, real hydrolysate with inhibitory compounds, pervaporation unit and increase in fermentor volume. Therefore a sequential scale-up approach was scheduled based on the following stages:

- **Stage 1:** Training on fermentation and elaboration of protocols. The main objective was upscaling the fermentation to evaluate the performance of the microorganism. Then, for this purpose a technician of GBL moved to CENER. As a result of this stage, four fermentations runs using synthetic media and increasing operating volumes in batch and fed-batch mode in different fermenters were carried out.
- **Stage 2:** Training on fermentation coupled to PV unit. In this stage the aim was to start working with the PV unit, therefore, 2 technicians from VITO moved to CENER. Three fermentation runs were carried out using synthetic sugars and higher volumes and starting to work in continuous mode with the PV unit. Along these assays, different strategies were tested in order to improve on one hand xylose consumption and as a consequence increase overall productivity; and on the other to work under optimal conditions for ABE products separation through the pervaporation unit.
- **Stage 3:** Fermentation & PV pilot runs (Figure 5). This final stage aimed at operating using real hydrolysate however due to the complexity of the feedstock and the presence of potential inhibitory compounds it was agreed to split the type of feedstock used for the experiments, thus at the beginning and for having a smoother operation, synthetic media would be used and once the stationary state were reached, wheat straw hydrolysate would be added. The number of runs carried out during this stage was 3.

Figure 5: Operation of fermentation and pervaporation unit at the pilot plant (Source: CENER/VITO)

Although stages 1 and 2 in the upscaling of the fermentation process run successfully with good sugar consumption rates, it was not possible to complete stage 3 due to the appearance of some technical problems.

6.4. ButaNexT mass balances

For the calculation of ButaNexT process' mass balances, real data for the pilot plant have been combined with the results obtained at the lab for the fermentation and pervaporation stages.

According to pilot plant results, the maximum

achieved conversion of wheat straw to sugars has been around 51.4% (dry biomass basis). This means approximately a 71% of the sugars (C6 and C5) available in the initial feedstock. This calculation involves two-step pretreatment and enzymatic hydrolysis processes.

Additionally, the sugar to ABE yield achieved in the bench scale runs carried out within the project has been 30% and the ABE recovery 70%. This means an achievable overall yield of c.11% which is acceptable as a first approach in the way to a demo plant.

7 BUTANEXT PROCESS ASSESSMENT

An environmental, social and techno-economic assessment has been carried out to understand the likely impacts of producing ligno-cellulosic biobutanol at commercial-scale. Given the current early stage of development of this technology, results are provisional and have a wide uncertainty range.

7.1. Environmental impact assessment

A GHG Assessment of biobutanol produced in a theoretical commercial-scale plant has been carried out. The butanol was assessed using a RED-compliant methodology, with data from the ButaNexT pilot plant, from process modelling carried out by the ButaNexT partners, and from the scientific literature. The biggest contributors to the overall GHG emissions are the enzymes, feedstock and the provision of heat and power to the plant.

A number of scenarios for improved plant performance were investigated: lower heat and power demand and high conversion efficiency of the process. Across these scenarios, the lowest GHG intensity of biobutanol (38 gCO₂eq./MJ) was achieved when both low heat and power demand and high conversion efficiency occur together, and heat and power is provided by on-site biomass combustion. This is equivalent to a GHG saving of 55% compared to the RED fossil fuel comparator, approaching the 60% GHG saving threshold that is required for biofuels produced in new plants under the RED.

As the biobutanol process is being developed and scaled up, key actions to further reduce GHG emissions are: improving overall conversion efficiency of feedstock to product, reducing heat and power demand of the biobutanol production process, for example through process integration, and maximizing use of by-products for on-site energy provision.

7.2. Social impact assessment

The social impact assessment has been carried out using an adapted version of the National Renewable Energy Laboratory's (NREL) open-source Jobs and Economic Development Impact (JEDI) model to assess the likely impacts of a commercial-scale biobutanol plant. The results indicate that there could be substantial job opportunities, particularly in the agriculture sector, from lignocellulosic biobutanol production.

The analysis suggests that if a commercial-scale biobutanol plant was constructed in Europe, considering specifically France, Denmark or Poland, then for every direct job created during plant operation, between 14 and 44 additional jobs could be generated, depending on the location of the plant. And for every direct Euro of value

added, between €172 and €592 of additional value added could be generated.

7.3. Techno-economic assessment

Finally a techno-economic assessment of a commercial-scale biobutanol production process, incorporating the technologies and improvements made over the course of the ButaNexT project has been carried out. Cash-flow modelling was used to estimate the levelised production cost of biobutanol, and the economic viability of the plant. The levelised biobutanol production cost in a 'baseline' scenario was roughly €2500/tonne, but improvements to the process and plant financing structure that may be expected in an 'nth plant' illustrated how this levelised production cost could potentially be reduced to below €1500/tonne.

The largest contribution to the levelised cost of biobutanol comes from the plant capital cost, and the cost of feedstock and enzymes. The cost of electricity could also have a large impact on the levelised cost, depending on how heat and power is provided to the plant. A sensitivity analysis demonstrated that reductions in capital, feedstock and enzyme costs had the greatest impact on the plant NPV (2). Increasing the overall yield of the process reduces the cost of all of these elements per unit of biobutanol produced.

8 BUTANOL PERFORMANCE AS A FUEL COMPONENT

8.1. Use of butanol in diesel engines

n-Butanol was proved to be a blend component in both gasoline and diesel fuels, with potential to reduce emissions. In both cases, the maximum butanol content is limited by startability problems.

A Euro 6 light-duty vehicle was tested following the New European Driving Cycle on a chassis dynamometer located in a climatic chamber with different blends of diesel and n-butanol, with up to 20% of the latter (vol.) and a ternary blend with 10% n-butanol, 10% biodiesel and 80% diesel, all of them in volume basis. Room temperatures were set at 24°C and -7°C. Binary butanol blends up to 16% (volume basis) and ternary blend showed benefits in particle number and particulate matter emissions upstream of the DPF (3) at any ambient condition, this implying a reduction in the frequency of regeneration. Benefits in engine efficiency were observed at cold ambient temperature (-7°C). Increases in NOx emissions were observed only at cold ambient temperature, while increases in CO and hydrocarbon emissions were found at any temperature for all blends tested. In general, including n-butanol as a blend component is beneficial for both performance and particulate emissions, but the blend concentration is limited by startability problems at very low ambient temperature. Also, including n-butanol affects soot reactivity positively, especially for those blends with highest oxygen content. The higher reactivity contributes to facilitate the particulate filter regeneration and consequently the fuel consumption in the engine. The following table shows a summary of the benefits and drawbacks of the selected butanol-diesel and butanol-biodiesel-diesel blends in ButaNexT project.

	Bu10D		Bu20D		Bu10B10D	
	-7°C	20°C	-7°C	20°C	-7°C	20°C
Specific fuel consumption (g/km)	Green	Orange	Green	Orange	Green	Orange
Specific energy consumption (MJ/km)	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green
Specific NOx (g/km)	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Green
Specific THC (g/km)	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
Specific CO (g/km)	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
Specific particulate number (#/km)	Orange	Green	Orange	Green	Orange	Orange
Particulate mass (g/km)	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green
Startability	Orange	Orange	Red	Orange	Orange	Orange

Table 2. Summary of the benefits/drawbacks of using n-butanol as a blend component in a diesel engine. All blends are compared with respect to diesel fuel (green: improves, orange: remains; red: worsens)

Including n-butanol as a blending component is beneficial for both performance and particulate emissions up to a certain butanol content, but this content is further limited by starting difficulties at very low ambient temperatures.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The main lessons learnt during the ButaNexT's pilot plant integration and scale-up assays have been the following:

- Wheat straw and miscanthus have been milled up to 0.5 mm using the micronising prototype designed and constructed by Técnicas Reunidas. In fact, improved productivities were obtained during the commissioning and production step increasing the production flow up to 7 kg/h for wheat straw.
- More than 500 kg of wheat straw slurry have been produced by CENER using an optimized thermal acid pretreatment that consists in subjecting the micronized material to 175°C with 4% w/w H2SO4 for just 5 minutes generating a pretreated material more prone to enzymatic hydrolysis of the cellulose content
- More than 500 kg of sugar rich hydrolysate (110 g/l sugars) have been produced by CENER through an enzymatic hydrolysis process using enzymes supplied by MetGen. The Enzyme cocktail used is an improved version that has increased overall enzymatic yields over 80-85%.
- Fermentation process using GBL's microorganism has been up scaled from 10 litres to 100 litres by CENER with the continuous support of Green Biologics and VITO. Fermentations batches have run successfully even more when the fermentation process is coupled with the pervaporation unit leading to a proper separation of the solvents while being produced.
- According to the results obtained in the fermentation, during the fed-batch mode, glucose and xylose conversion were near completion. To this end, the

fermentor was integrated with a POMS pervaporation membrane module for this first time on pilot scale.

- The mass balances of the integrated pilot plant have been updated according to the real data obtained during the assays.

However, it has not been possible to complete a pilot run using wheat straw hydrolysate in the time frames of the project due to the some technical problems. Nevertheless, and although the final results have not been as complete as expected, we think the encountered hurdles are critical points that need to be overcome, but are not of a fundamental nature related to the developed technology. Furthermore, the gathered data can be used to properly reevaluate and optimize the pilot-scale design of fermentation integrated with pervaporation.

Finally, it should be noted that while these results represent a useful pilot plant level demonstration the mass balance analysis shows that significant levels of improvement would be needed to match conversion yields seen in work packages focussed on sub processes or seen elsewhere. So, the conversion of biomass to sugars at c.51.4% (dry biomass basis) compares to an industry expectation of c.55%, the sugar to ABE yield of c.30% compares to laboratory data of c.35% and the ABE product in broth to ABE recovery of c.70% compares to an expectation using distillation of c.99%. Taken together this overall yield of c.11% compares to an expectation of what could be achieved commercially of c.19% (dry biomass to recovered ABE). Assumptions reflecting these higher levels were utilized as a potentially achievable scenario in the techno-economic analysis and for the life cycle analysis.

5 NOTES

- (1) ABE: fermentation process named after the three products; acetone, butanol and ethanol.
- (2) NPV: Net Present Value
- (3) DPF: Diesel particulate filter

6 REFERENCES

- [1] European Environmental Agency. <https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/indicators/transport-emissions-of-greenhouse-gases/transport-emissions-of-greenhouse-gases-10>
- [2] Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda 2016. European Biofuels Technology Platform. Innovation driving sustainable biofuels June 2016
- [3] https://ec.europa.eu/clima/policies/strategies/2030_en
- [4] <https://ec.europa.eu/energy/en/news/commission-proposes-new-rules-consumer-centred-clean-energy-transition>
- [5] Alternative Fuels Data Center. US DOE. <https://www.afdc.energy.gov/fuels/emerging/biobutanol.html>
- [6] Sauer, M. Industrial production of acetone and butanol by fermentation—100 years later. FEMS Microbiology Letters, 363, 2016, fnw134
- [7] Del Campo et al. ButaNexT. Next Generation Biobutanol. Proceedings of the 24th European Biomass Conference. Amsterdam, June 2016.

- [8] Del Campo et al. Paving the way for a next generation biobutanol (ButaNexT). Proceedings of the 25th European Biomass Conference. Stockholm, June 2017.

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8 LOGO SPACE

More information about ButaNexT:

<http://www.butanext.eu>